

Grant Agreement Number: 723016

Project acronym: **INFRAMIX**

Project full title: INFRAMIX - Road INFRAstructure ready for MIXed vehicle traffic flows

D.6.1

Communication strategy and Plan

Due delivery date: 30.11.2017

Actual delivery date: 27.12.2017

Organization name of lead participant for this deliverable: **ENI**

Project co-funded by the European Commission within Horizon 2020		
Dissemination level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

Project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (2014 – 2020)

Document Control Sheet

Deliverable number:	6.1
Deliverable responsible:	ENI
Work package:	6
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Document Revision History			
Version	Date	Modifications Introduced	
0.1	30.08.2017	TOC	ENI
0.2	18.09.2017	Revision of TOC	ENI
0.3	25.11.2017	First complete draft	ENI
0.4	28.11.2017	Minor corrections	ENI
0.5	01.11.2017	Submitted for review	ENI
1.0	27.12.2017	Final version	ENI
1.1	10.01.2018	Minor corrections, final version	ENI
1.2	23.01.2018	Final version ready for submission	ENI

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	6
1. Introduction	7
1.1 Aim of the project	7
1.2 Purpose of document	7
2. General Communication and Dissemination Objectives	8
2.1 Background	8
2.2 Dissemination Objectives	8
3. Communication and Dissemination target groups	9
3.1 Industry	9
3.2 Infrastructure operators and Road authorities	9
3.3 Public administration	9
3.4 Relevant EU, national and international initiatives	9
3.5 Standardisation bodies	10
3.6 European and international organisations and technical communities	10
3.7 Scientific and research community	10
3.8 EC staff/politicians and relevant European Organizations	10
3.9 End users	10
3.10 Key influencers / Publications	11
3.11 General public	11
4. Communication and Dissemination Plan	12
4.1 First phase activities	12
4.2 Second phase activities	12
4.3 Third phase activities	12
4.4 Activities after the project end	13
4.5 Time table of results	13
5. Communication and Dissemination tools	15
5.1 Establishing INFRAMIX as a brand	15
5.1.1 Project Logo	15
5.1.2 Project brochure	15
5.1.3 General presentation	16
5.1.4 Roll-up banner and posters	16
5.2 Media	17
5.2.1 Promotional video	17
5.2.2 Press releases	17
5.2.3 Sectorial Newspapers/Journals publications	18
5.3 On-line tools	18
5.4 Website	19
5.4.1 Newsletter	20
5.4.2 Social media	21
5.5 Project wrap-up and preparing for exploitation	22

5.6	Dissemination versus Communication channels	22
6.	Dissemination toolbox.....	23
6.1	Dissemination approval procedure	23
6.2	Open access	23
6.3	Results timeline of expected communicable results	24
6.4	Related initiatives	25
7.	INFRAMIX events and visibility at external events	27
7.1	INFRAMIX events	27
7.2	INFRAMIX End Users' Group events.....	27
7.3	External events.....	27
8.	Measuring the effectiveness of activities	29
8.1	Summary of Key performance indicators.....	29
8.2	Activities performed during the first 6 months of project.....	30
9.	Conclusion	32
10.	References.....	33
	ANNEX I – H2020 guidelines	34
	H2020 Dissemination Guidelines	34
	Promoting the action — Visibility of EU funding: Communication activities by beneficiaries	34
	Dissemination of results — Open access — Visibility of EU funding	34
	Open access to scientific publications	36
	Communication versus Dissemination.....	36
	ANNEX II - Other Social media	37
	Facebook	37
	Wikipedia	37
	SlideShare	38
	Open access repository.....	38
	Annex III - Dissemination approval procedure.....	40
	ANNEX IV – Template for Procedure for Publication	41
	ANNEX V - Overview of resources	42
	Overview of deliverables in WP6.....	42
	Overview of person-months per participant.....	42
	Work plan.....	43
	Overview of dissemination material direct costs	43
	ANNEX VI – Dissemination actions	44
	ANNEX VII – Data Privacy aspects concerning dissemination.....	47

List of Figures

Figure 1 – Phases of the activities	12
Figure 2 – Logo	15
Figure 3 - INFRAMIX knowledge management and protection strategy in the wider context of dissemination	24
Figure 4 – Examples of coverage of the project in Spanish media	44
Figure 5 - Dr. Angelos Amditis (ICCS) presents Inframix project and infrastructure preparation for coexistence of automated and conventional vehicles at the ITS World Congress 2017, Montreal.....	45
Figure 6 - Project Kick-off meeting.....	46

List of Tables

Table 1 - INFRAMIX results along timeline.....	13
Table 2 - INFRAMIX communication tools and audience groups	15
Table 3 - INFRAMIX media tools and audience groups	17
Table 4 – Initial list of business and scientific Journals	18
Table 5 - INFRAMIX online tools and audience groups.....	19
Table 6 – Schedule of newsletters for INFRAMIX project	21
Table 7 – Dissemination versus communication channels	22
Table 8 - INFRAMIX deliverables and target groups	24
Table 9 - INFRAMIX planned scientific publications	25
Table 10 – Potential events for INFRAMIX	28
Table 11 - INFRAMIX Key Performance Indicators for Communication & Dissemination.....	29
Table 12 - INFRAMIX dissemination actions up to month 6	30
Table 13 - Overview WP6 deliverables	42
Table 14 - Overview of person-months per participant	42
Table 15 - Overview of work plan for WP6	43
Table 16 - Overview of dissemination costs	43

Executive Summary

INFRAMIX will help prepare road infrastructure to support the coexistence of conventional and automated vehicles. Its main objective is to design, upgrade, adapt and test both physical and digital elements of the road infrastructure. The key outcome will be a “hybrid” road infrastructure able to handle the transition period and become the basis for future automated transport systems. The project developments will be assessed via simulation and on real stretches of advanced highways. This will help to ensure that the proposed adaptations will not jeopardize safety, efficiency and quality of service and will be appreciated by the users.

INFRAMIX Project activities have set ambitious targets for the adaptation of existing road infrastructure for the adoption of the automated vehicle. A concise dissemination strategy, therefore, is of major importance for the maximization of the project’s impact to the scientific community, the industry, the society and for the successful deployment of its results. The consortium’s intention is to widely disseminate the existence of the project goals and results not only within Europe but also internationally, in order to highlight Europe as a major force worldwide in the relevant scientific and industrial field. In this document, the communication and dissemination strategy and plans designed for this purpose are presented.

This deliverable includes the communication, dissemination and liaison strategy and plan to be followed within the project. The dissemination strategy defines the goals for the dissemination activities of the project. These are being achieved by reaching the specified communication and dissemination target groups through defined dissemination channels.

1. Introduction

1.1 Aim of the project

INFRAMIX will help prepare road infrastructure to support the coexistence of conventional and automated vehicles.

Its main objective is to design, upgrade, adapt and test both physical and digital elements of the road infrastructure. The key outcome will be a “hybrid” road infrastructure able to handle the transition period and become the basis for future automated transport systems. The project developments will be assessed via simulation and on real stretches of advanced highways. This will help to ensure that the proposed adaptations will not jeopardize safety, efficiency, quality of service and will be appreciated by the users.

INFRAMIX builds on three traffic scenarios: *dynamic lane assignment*, *roadwork zones* and *bottlenecks*. INFRAMIX addresses mainly highways, as they are expected to be the initial hosts of mixed traffic, but the key results can also be transferred to urban roads.

1.2 Purpose of document

INFRAMIX Project activities have set ambitious targets for the adaptation of existing road infrastructure for the adoption of the automated vehicle. A concise dissemination strategy, therefore, is of major importance for the maximization of the project’s impact to the scientific community, the industry, the society and for the successful deployment of its results. The consortium’s intention is to widely disseminate the existence of the project goals and results not only within Europe but also internationally, in order to highlight Europe as a major force worldwide in the relevant scientific and industrial field. In this document, the communication and dissemination strategy and plans designed for this purpose are presented.

The dissemination strategy defines the goals for the dissemination activities of the project. These are being achieved by reaching the specified dissemination target groups through defined dissemination channels. The ways to reach the target groups depends on the stage of the work progress of the project. While at the early stages of the project the dissemination is concentrated on presentations of the idea and concept of the work to be deployed, at later stages the dissemination task will focus on presenting the achieved developments and results. All these are described in the dissemination roadmap which provides a draft outline of the dissemination activities and their presented content per year of the project.

Dissemination activities are important for the Consortium also on a partner level. Making the Consortium partners’ competencies known can prove beneficial for promoting their activities as well. It is expected that regardless the partnership in the specific project WP, all partners will take part in Communication and Dissemination activities even at a different level. This contribution can take several forms, from artistic design in the dissemination material to scientific review of papers in workshops, conference participation, exhibitions etc. Thus, it is essential that all partners have an overall idea of their planned dissemination activities either for INFRAMIX purposes exclusively or for general purposes where INFRAMIX will also be represented. The dissemination activities are managed by the Dissemination Leader and specific dissemination procedures are followed which are also described within the document.

In order to keep the alignment of the communication strategy with the findings and results of the project as well as the impact of the previous dissemination actions, this deliverable will be revised and updated in M18 and M36.

2. General Communication and Dissemination Objectives

2.1 Background

The overall aim of the INFRAMIX communication and dissemination framework is to promote the project, its mission and results to a wide range of stakeholders at European, national, regional, local and international levels. It is important to communicate with a far-reaching audience and each level of governance has different stakeholders which INFRAMIX needs to address. Therefore, the project will adopt a cross-level dissemination approach.

The project also aims to establish the project and its tools as a reference point for the adaptation of existing road infrastructure for the adoption of the automated vehicle. This aspect is increasingly important for the legacy of the project and aims to encourage the actual take-up and deployment of the INFRAMIX solution after the project has finished.

A key objective of INFRAMIX is to develop effective communication interfaces and dissemination channels. All of the dissemination tools will have a clear message and explain the objectives and mission of the project in a consistent and coherent way. All of the separate communication tools (described later) will aim to attract the interest of all of the target groups and will be designed to match the common project identity.

The project will also communicate the role of the EU and the H2020 Programme through all of the communication and dissemination channels. It is important to promote the programme supporting INFRAMIX and showcase similar successful projects to boost the overall success of the project.

2.2 Dissemination Objectives

As said before, the overall objective is to promote the project, its mission and results to the groups of stakeholders described in Section 3, and achieve the largest possible impact, to build consensus and to raise awareness around the achievements of innovations and best practices developed in the project, and to exploit the results to benefit the implementation of the INFRAMIX key innovations.

Through different targeted activities and dedicated communication tools, the INFRAMIX Dissemination Strategy includes:

- Define a dissemination framework, with dedicated dissemination tools and channels which are adapted to respective target groups
- Organise and facilitating events with input from all WPs
- Establish synergy in dissemination with relevant other initiatives
- Present INFRAMIX at internal and external events

3. Communication and Dissemination target groups

3.1 Industry

This group includes the following sub-groups:

- OEMs / Vehicle manufacturers
- Vehicle technology suppliers
- Infrastructure technology suppliers
- Other ICT solutions providers

This group comprises both business and technical experts. The communication direction can be both external to the consortium and internal towards the project partners.

3.2 Infrastructure operators and Road authorities

This group includes the organizations (public or private) responsible for the correct managing of the road infrastructure. It includes both individual organizations and/or associations (ERF, CEDR, ASECAP, ERTRAC, BAST¹, etc).

3.3 Public administration

It refers to the decision makers, city planners and other public authorities at different geographical levels, as urban areas, regional administrations, countries and different country clusters. They can be responsible for the design, construction, operation and/or legislation of the road transportation in public infrastructures.

3.4 Relevant EU, national and international initiatives

Dissemination within the research community is one of the pre-requisites for successful project implementation. Knowledge exchange is crucial for assessing the state-of-the-art, project planning and evaluating project results.

This target group will be addressed via different ways: individually, within the framework of international organisations in which researchers maintain international exchange and cooperation, and by official contact at project level.

Some of the potential projects are as follows:

- Adaptive, www.adaptive-ip.eu
- AutoMate, www.automate-project.eu
- AutoNet2030, www.autonet2030.eu
- BRAVE, www.brave-project.eu
- CARTRE, www.connectedautomateddriving.eu/about-us/cartre
- CoEXist, www.h2020-coexist.eu
- ConVeX, www.qualcomm.com/news/onq/2017/02/24/accelerating-c-v2x-toward-5g-autonomous-driving
- Dragon, www.cedr-dragon.eu

¹ Bundesanstalt für Straßenwesen (german federal organisation for street management)

- interACT, www.interact-roadautomation.eu
- L3Pilot, l3pilot.eu
- MAVEN, www.maven-its.eu
- PROVIDENTIA, www.fortiss.org/forschung/projekte/providentia/
- SCOUT, www.connectedautomateddriving.eu/about-us/scout/
- SENSKIN, www.senskin.eu
- TRAMAN21, www.traman21.tuc.gr
- TransAID, www.transaid.eu
- TrustVehicle, www.trustvehicle.eu

This effort will have an international scope. European, but also overseas high-profile colleagues involved in similar research activities will be contacted for collaboration.

3.5 Standardisation bodies

This target group will focus on entities as European Telecommunications Standards Institute, ETSI, or Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE).

3.6 European and international organisations and technical communities

This is a wide group of individual associations (i.e. industry associations as EUCAR, OICA, ACEA, VDA, ANFAC, SAE; other relevant EC/national projects; ETP's such as ERTRAC; technology groups as FEHRL, ERTICO, Amsterdam Group, C2C-CC, TM2.0 Platform, ADASIS Forum, NDS Association, AASHTO, FHWA, AUVSI, TRB and the Trilateral EU-US-Japan Automation Working Group in Road Transportation), at European, national and international level, which have significant multiplier potential as associations representing transport authorities and members of the industry.

3.7 Scientific and research community

The results of the project will be broadly disseminated to the scientific community through participation in the most important academic conferences and related events. Please, refer to section 7.3 for a detailed list of events.

3.8 EC staff/politicians and relevant European Organizations

This group includes EC staff/politicians, relevant European Organizations (ERTICO, etc), policy advisors and key opinion creators.

This will facilitate a clearer overall understanding of the topic and consequently will provide an evident support for decision making activities at higher level.

This group includes standardization fora and initiatives where the results and project recommendations will be communicated.

3.9 End users

The following target groups have been identified up to now: Drivers associations; Professional transport associations; Safety groups:

- IRU World Transport Organization (www.iru.org)
- Association for European Transport (www.aetransport.org)
- Drivers associations at global level as FIA (www.fia.com) or FIM (www.fim-live.com) or national/regional level (as, for example, RACE Real Automovil Club España – www.race.es - or RACC Real Automovil Club Catalunya - www.racc.es)
- ETSC European Transport Safety Council (www.etsc.eu)
- MOVINGs International Safety Association (www.moving-roadsafety.com)
- ADAC (www.adac.de)

3.10 Key influencers / Publications

EU wide, national, regional, online and specialist publications. Please, refer to section 5.2.3 for a detailed list of publications.

3.11 General public

Informing and communicating with the public as well as fostering societal debate have already become integral constituents of the portfolio of European initiatives. For this audience, key-messages should focus on the overall concept rather than on specific technical solutions.

4. Communication and Dissemination Plan

The selection of the appropriate dissemination channel and the respective message to be disseminated heavily depends on the stage that the project is at each specific moment. During the early phases of the project, the focus is on transmitting the project concept and the idea of the research work. Towards the end of the project, however, more technical presentations and publications can be realised as new findings will be available. Having this in mind, the Communication and Dissemination plan has been determined and is presented below. This Plan provides the outline of how the dissemination channels and materials will be used for reaching each of the specified target group per year of the project.

Figure 1 – Phases of the activities

4.1 First phase activities

During the first part of the project, the dissemination activities are aiming to generally inform the public, relevant research, academic and automated vehicle community and all relevant stakeholders on INFRAMIX objectives and expected results. These activities are setting the basis for the whole communication and dissemination policy since most of the communication and dissemination material will be produced at this stage and will be used for the duration of the project. The informative leaflets and roll-up have been designed and are going to be disseminated to various events. In addition, the website has already been developed including information about the project and it will be updated regularly. The publications and presentations of this period will describe mainly the project concept and research methodology. At this stage, the main activities are related to Communication, rather than Dissemination.

This phase covers from project start to first findings obtained, approximately in M18.

4.2 Second phase activities

During the second part of the project, some results will already be available. Thus, the aim of the communication and dissemination activities within this period will be to publish the first findings and describe the future work to be performed. The research community, industry and policy-making authorities and decision-making stakeholders, end users etc., will form the target groups of the publications and project presentations to be performed during this phase. Technical papers will be submitted to scientific conferences as well as to workshops and events. The communication and dissemination material will be the same as developed in the first phase while the website will be continuously updated with newer project achievements.

This phase covers from first findings to completion of the set of tools, approximately in M29.

4.3 Third phase activities

During the final part of the project there will be a major effort of disseminating the project results to all target groups using every dissemination channel available. Press releases and mass media will be employed for transmitting the INFRAMIX message. Technical papers presenting the final results will be published to journals and to various international and

European industry and scientific conferences, while demonstrations of solutions and prototypes will be given at relevant exhibitions. At this phase several papers submissions to scientific journals are expected. The website will continuously be updated with the latest developments and information and the final project deliverables will be available for downloading.

4.4 Activities after the project end

Even after the end of the project, there is still a possibility to support and promote the project impact to the wider community. All public final results will be available at INFRAMIX web site. It will be sustained after the end of the project for at least five years in order to provide all interested stakeholders with information on project achievements and findings and details on contact persons for more information.

4.5 Time table of results

The table below includes the planned timeline for the availability of the project findings, as well as the expected communicable results and the respective audience addressed:

Table 1 - INFRAMIX results along timeline

Id	Time	Date	Expected results	Audience addressed
R1	M06	Nov'17	- Requirements catalogue, Analysis of the three traffic scenarios and definition of related use cases resulting in requirements	- Industry - Infrastructure operators, road authorities - Relevant initiatives - General Public
R2	M18	Nov'18	- Simulations tools and relevant models ready - Traffic state estimation and traffic control algorithms available - Plan for demonstrations and testing finalized	- Industry - Infrastructure operators, road authorities - Relevant initiatives - EC&EU authorities - Influencers
R3	M24	May'19	- Digital and physical infrastructure elements designed and developed - New visual signs and elements - HD maps and electronic road horizon (*) - Traffic management strategies (*)	- Industry - Infrastructure operators, road authorities - Relevant initiatives - EC&EU authorities - Influencers
R4	M26	Jul'19	- Infrastructure classification scheme available	- Industry - Infrastructure operators, road authorities - Relevant initiatives - EC&EU authorities
R5	M30	Nov'19	- Aggregated data available for evaluation (*)	- Industry - Infrastructure operators, road authorities
R6	M36	May'20	- Evaluation, impact analysis and	- Industry

Id	Time	Date	Expected results	Audience addressed
			users' appreciation results - Exploitation plans (*) - Roadmap towards fully automated transport systems	- Infrastructure operators, road authorities - Relevant initiatives - EC&EU authorities - Influencers - General Public

(*) These results may contain confidential information. Each of them will be analysed to define the public contents; at the same time, the existence and purpose itself of the result could be of use in the communication activities.

5. Communication and Dissemination tools

The communication and dissemination toolbox is divided in several sections:

- Establishing INFRAMIX as a brand
- Mass media
- On-line tools

These elements will be elaborated in the following sections. The related initial material described in these sections is presented in the document INFRAMIX D6.2 Communications kit.

5.1 Establishing INFRAMIX as a brand

The following table summarises the subjects (further described later) with the related results and the expected audience:

Table 2 - INFRAMIX communication tools and audience groups

Subject	Related Results	Audience								
		Industry	Infr. Ops & Road auth	Public admin	EU&Nat org and Tech	Scientific & R+I com.	EC and EU stakeh	End users	Key influencers	General public
Logo	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Roll-up	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Brochure	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
General presentation	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	

5.1.1 Project Logo

A logo (abbreviation of logotype) is a graphic mark, emblem, or symbol commonly used to aid and promote instant public recognition.

The project logo (Figure 2) has been produced electronically in high-definition PNG format

Figure 2 – Logo

5.1.2 Project brochure

Description

Project brochure is a presentation of the project concept, challenges and characteristics of developed solutions. It should be presented with the use of graphics, pictures, icons and graphs reflecting the project idea.

Use:

INFRAMIX brochure will illustrate its concept, proposed solutions and expected impact. It will be produced electronically in PDF format and made available on the project website. An English version will be printed and will be used in every available occasion - at INFRAMIX events and meetings with stakeholders as well as at external events such as conferences, fairs and exhibitions, seminars and other meetings with industry. The content of this brochure will be updated during the project, if necessary, to include final INFRAMIX results.

The electronic version could be produced in different languages (based on the requests and availability of the partners of the project) to reach the widest possible target audience in several countries. Since the purpose of the brochure is to have a lifespan that will encompass the whole duration of the project it will be written in an open style, so that it is fresh and appealing for catching the audience.

We estimate to distribute 1.000 brochures during the different events where INFRAMIX and/or INFRAMIX partners could participate.

5.1.3 General presentation

Description

The general project presentation is an electronic presentation composed by several general slides introducing the main project idea. The text is in most cases presented in bullet points accompanied by pictures, icons, links to websites, etc.

Use:

The general project presentation will be used during different events, including internal project events such as project workshops, meetings with stakeholders and external events such as conferences, fairs and exhibitions and seminars. The purpose is to assist partners to communicate INFRAMIX solutions, expected impact and at a later stage initial achievements and results, in a consolidated and consistent way both internally and externally. The presentation will be made in English and should be translated into other partners languages if needed for the communication with the stakeholders in partner countries.

5.1.4 Roll-up banner and posters

Description

The project roll-ups and posters are large one-page graphical presentations or pictures of the project idea. The design of project roll-ups and posters is of high relevance and therefore it must follow the "corporate identity" pattern (logo, images, colours, fonts). Its purpose is to capture attention and advertise the project. Its basic content should include:

- Acronym and name of the project
- Logos and tagline for the project

Use

During the project, roll-ups and posters will be designed for specific events or purposes. They will be used to provide an eye-catching and thought-provoking presentation, and to include contact or website details giving ready access to further information. It will be printed and used at exhibitions, conferences and public meetings.

5.2 Media

The following table summarises the media related measures (described later in detail) with the related results and the expected audience:

Table 3 - INFRAMIX media tools and audience groups

Measures	Related Results	Audience								
		Industry	Infr. Ops & Road auth	Public admin	EU&Nat org and Tech	Scientific & R+I com.	EC and EU stakeh	End users	Key influencers	General public
Promotional video(s)	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Press releases	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Generalist Journals publications	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Specialised Journals publications	General communication / Focused results	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

5.2.1 Promotional video

Description

The project video is an interactive presentation in the form of a movie briefly introducing the project idea, its results and characteristics of developed solutions using simple messages.

Use

It will be presented in English and made available through the project web site and other available channels, platforms such as YouTube, forums supporting the project realisation and in social media.

The video will be enriched in the course of project including actual developments demonstrated at the INFRAMIX test sites. The different versions of the INFRAMIX video will be also displayed both at INFRAMIX events and at relevant conferences and exhibitions.

It is planned to produce two (2) videos of the project during its duration, the second one being more comprehensive (presenting final project results).

5.2.2 Press releases

Description

Press releases are intended to communicate the project’s progress or announce important achievements. A press release is usually a one-page note presenting the message briefly, using simple language.

Use

All project members are expected to contribute to the dissemination of project results through appropriate press releases in their respective countries throughout the duration of

the project. Especially WP leaders are requested to produce press releases on the results achieved. When such a press release is published, an electronic copy must be sent to the dissemination leader, in order to be uploaded to the project website. In addition, some details should be given by the partner in charge: source, publication date, target audience.

A press release template will be included as part of INFRAMIX D6.2 Communications kit.

5.2.3 Sectorial Newspapers/Journals publications

Description

Publication of the project in Newspapers and Journals in the form of articles (not advertisement).

Use

The project partners will be asked to explore the possibility to present the project in sectorial Newspapers/Journals according to the cost/benefit principle.

List of potential business and scientific journals (to be expanded during the project):

Table 4 – Initial list of business and scientific Journals

Business and Scientific Journals	Comment
Horizon Magazine	
Research*eu results magazine	
Futuris Magazine	
Thinking Highways	
IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Magazine (ITSM)	
ITS International	
International Journal of Vehicle Autonomous Systems	Possible open access
SAE Connected and Automated Vehicles	
SAE Automotive Engineering	
Springer - Journal of Modern Transportation	Possible open access
Intelligent Transport – Magazine	
Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems	Possible open access
Traffic Engineering and Control (TEC) magazine	
Traffic Technology International	
Intertraffic World	
Routes/Roads - World Road Association	
www.worldhighways.com	
Automotive News	
IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters (GRSL)	
GeoInformatics Magazine	
ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information	Possible open access
IEEE Spectrum	General Technical Scope
Open Science Journal	General Technical Scope
R&D Magazine - rdmag.com	General Technical Scope
Science Business	General Technical Scope

During the first year, INFRAMIX plans to publish at least 3 scientific papers in international journals or conferences. Please, check section 8.1 for extended KPI figures.

5.3 On-line tools

In this section, several on-line tools are reviewed. For each one, an analysis is performed to define its potential use related to the objectives of the internet community presence of INFRAMIX; the final goal is to select the most suitable ones, describing the potential use of

them.

The following table summarises the on-line tools related measures (further described later) with the related results and the expected audience:

Table 5 - INFRAMIX online tools and audience groups

Measures	Related Results	Audience								
		Industry	Infr. Ops & Road auth	Public admin	EU&Nat org and Tech	Scientific & R+I com.	EC and EU stakeh	End users	Key influencers	General public
Web site	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Newsletters	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Social media	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

5.4 Website

Description

As stated in the INFRAMIX Description of Work, the project website is a major channel for visibility of the INFRAMIX project: it describes the project and its aims and highlights its results to be achieved. The project web site also serves as an interactive tool for internal and external communication. It provides a place to share public documents, updates on the current research phases and results, presents further developments and informs about upcoming events.

Use

As said before, the website (www.inframix.eu) will be the key stone for the building of the internet community for INFRAMIX. It will centralize the content provided from the project among the other web 2.0 tools, trying to organize a common approach among all them and taking profit of the different features of the others.

Recognizing that the project website/portal is an important resource in disseminating information about the project, facilitating collaboration amongst partners, and bringing together a diverse and scattered community of interest around the project's activities, we have foreseen the following activities to improve its usability and features, and to market it for increased traffic and

Figure 1 INFRAMIX web site
www.inframix.eu

searchability:

- Improving and updating content to be relevant and rich in keywords density;
- Introducing Search Engine Marketing parameters such as keyword density, quality titles, headers and images, etc.
- A Sign In online form for people interested in the topics of INFRAMIX is included in every page to subscribe and receive INFRAMIX updates and newsletters. This way, the website will serve also as one of the channels that will be used for the expansion of the INFRAMIX End Users' Group.
- A download area has also been created, where public project deliverables, open access publications, presentations, newsletters, press articles and communication material will be available for download.

The goal is to make the portal a true source of information and contact point for further collaboration. The website content will be kept simple so as to be understandable by non-technical audiences too and will include details on the project vision, concept, objectives, proposed technologies, consortium members, test sites and expected impact.

During the first year, we have the goal of 250 unique page views per month, enabled by the mentioned actions as well as SEO techniques. Please, check section 8.1 for extended KPI figures.

Community Manager

To execute this strategy and to mobilize the different efforts to provide contents and materials for all these tools, it is necessary to define a single responsible for these activities. This role will need:

- To be aware of the technical and scientific activities and findings of the project;
- To be aware of the different dissemination actions of the project;
- To channelize the feedback received from the audience;
- To coordinate the consortium partners to enhance the impact of the dissemination tools;
- To gather all this information to provide contents and materials for the Web tools, especially creating an open discussion around the concepts of the project.

The Dissemination manager will initially act as Community Manager of INFRAMIX.

5.4.1 Newsletter

Description

A newsletter is a regularly distributed publication generally about one main topic that is of interest to its subscribers. Newspapers and leaflets are types of newsletters. Additionally, newsletters delivered electronically via email (e-Newsletters) have gained rapid acceptance for the same reasons as email, in general, has gained popularity over printed correspondence. Newsletters have become common source of informing specific audience on issues of their interest. For example, newsletters are distributed at schools, to inform parents about things that happen in that school.

Sending newsletters to customers is a common marketing strategy, which can have benefits and drawbacks. General attributes of newsletters include news and upcoming events of the related organization, as well as contact information for general inquiries.

Use

The project newsletter will be also a very important tool for the communication of the project

goals. Concerning the use for the internet community building, a double method will be used: 1) the existing versions will be available at the website; 2) it will be actively distributed through the social media, through a mailing list and, also, through the project consortium partners.

The INFRAMIX newsletters will be oriented to offer information to project stakeholders, focusing on aims and results instead of in project internal organization or activities. In each newsletter we plan to include the most important highlights (in terms of results) during the period covered.

A total of five e-newsletters will be produced, one every six months (starting in M12) during the project to keep the INFRAMIX community informed about the project's progress and results. Short and snappy articles on the project's activities and demonstrations will give a good impression to the different target groups INFRAMIX intends to reach including the members of the INFRAMIX End User Group, as well as non-technical audiences via social media and direct emailing. The newsletter will also provide an opportunity to expand the project's database via the subscription option on the INFRAMIX website.

Table 6 – Schedule of newsletters for INFRAMIX project

Number	Due date
E-newsletter 1	June 2018
E-newsletter 2	December 2018
E-newsletter 3	June 2019
E-newsletter 4	December 2019
E-newsletter 5	May 2020

The related KPI include the newsletter distributed to 50 signed persons at M12, achieved through a mix of actions on the website and other social media. Please, check section 8.1 for extended KPI figures.

Please, check Annexes section for additional information about data privacy handling concerning Newsletter and mailing lists management.

5.4.2 Social media

Next to classic electronic channels like email and a web portal, Social Media will need consideration. Because of the ease of communication and the groups involved, the dynamics of communication will be intense, and messages can get warped if conversations are left alone, once INFRAMIX news have been picked up by certain Social Media. Social Media will be applied in specific situations like indicated hereafter:

- Twitter (@INFRAMIX): to be applied at specific conferences and workshops, using a hashtag assigned by the conference/workshop organizer. The '#INFRAMIX' combined with a hashtag of the conference/workshop will be used for specific workshops.
- LinkedIn (INFRAMIX Project, <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12078841>): will be used to create interest groups with focused discussions and to post blogs and newsfeeds.

Other social media such as YouTube, SlideShare or Wikipedia are considered in Annexes section.

Two social media campaigns will be organised in the course of the project. The campaigns will aim to involve interested stakeholders in the ongoing discussion regarding the need for improving road infrastructure to facilitate the gradual insertion of automated vehicles on our

roads and be prepared for mixed traffic scenarios. Social media activities will also assist partners to identify and invite interested experts to join the INFRAMIX End Users' Group.

Furthermore, the consortium members will make use of their companies'/organisations' individual social networking sites to diffuse project messages and discuss project innovations and proposed solutions with their contacts. INFRAMIX consortium will also seek every opportunity to diffuse project achievements through the H2020 related social media accounts.

During the first year, we expect 100 twitter followers reached by cross following actions, and 80 LinkedIn group members, achieved through an activity and collaboration of the Consortium members professional accounts, as well as communication of the addresses using posters, flyers, website, etc. Please, check section 8.1 for extended KPI figures.

5.5 Project wrap-up and preparing for exploitation

This final phase of the project will present the overall results of the INFRAMIX project. The final event will be the main opportunity to showcase the INFRAMIX results. This event will also be the start of the post-project INFRAMIX take-up.

5.6 Dissemination versus Communication channels²

Table 7 – Dissemination versus communication channels

Channels	Communication	Dissemination
Project website – General presentation pages	X	
Project website – Specific pages dedicated to outputs		X
Mailing lists & Contact databases – General	X	X
Social media	X	
External channels – Generalist	X	
External channels – Specialised, sectorial, targeted		X
Project events – Presentation of project outputs		X
External events – Announcements, brochures and flyers, etc	X	
External events – Presentation of project results		X
Publications in scientific magazines		X

² For a discussion concerning the differences between Dissemination and Communication in the H2020 arena, please check Annex concerning H2020 Guidelines

6. Dissemination toolbox

6.1 Dissemination approval procedure

Following the INFRAMIX Consortium Agreement, a procedure for the approval for publication of scientific/technical materials have been defined. Please, refer to the Annex section for a detailed description.

6.2 Open access

Article 29.2 of the Grant Agreement states that “*each beneficiary **MUST ensure open access** (free of charge, online access for any user) to ALL peer reviewed scientific publication relating its results.*” INFRAMIX will apply two different models:

- Green model. After an embargo period benefiting the publisher, the scientific author/s publishes the article/paper in an open repository.
- Gold model. The scientific author allows (i.e. by payment) to the publisher to allow immediate open access to readers.

A major effort will be made to address the publication of peer-reviewed scientific papers and articles to renowned and high-impact journals and conferences proceedings. As said, INFRAMIX will pursue a hybrid approach regarding the specific open access model it will follow (see figure 2). It will sustain the Green Model (self-archiving) for the majority of its publications, while for 2 or 3 key publications, such as the infrastructure classification scheme, it will follow the Gold model (open access publishing). The reasoning behind this hybrid approach is the publication fees associated with the Gold model, which are not negligible. Thus, for the latter case, dedicated resources have been allocated in the budget breakdown.

The intention of the project, in line with the spirit of Horizon 2020, is to promote INFRAMIX scientific results in an open access mode either through specific repositories and the INFRAMIX project website (in case of Green Model) or directly by exploiting the scientific publisher resources (in case of Gold Model). Concurrently, the project will apply the Creative Commons Attribution Licence to published work to allow its download, read, print, distribution, copy and use, as long as the original authors and source are cited. The INFRAMIX website is the communication platform for the dissemination of knowledge, material and results, publishing grey literature information to the general public or to a restricted group (the consortium and the EC), in accordance to the consortium’s knowledge management and IPR policies. All INFRAMIX data (e.g. customer-sourced information) that encompass personal data protection or privacy and IPR or form the basis to the project’s business model will be stored in the project repository and will not be publicly disclosed. Following this hybrid strategy, the partnership will benefit from the proliferation of search engines and indexation techniques, while recognising OA benefits to the increased access and impact of INFRAMIX innovations, assisting an effective knowledge sharing.

Figure 3 - INFRAMIX knowledge management and protection strategy in the wider context of dissemination

6.3 Results timeline of expected communicable results

Dissemination is supported by publications, i.e., deliverables considered as public and communications to academic and technical publications and events.

The following table lists the public project deliverables, including the ID of the results that link with Table 1. Given its interest, some confidential deliverables have been also included in the table (identified with the * sign): each of them will be analysed to delimitate its public contents, if any; in addition, the mere existence and purpose itself of the result could be of use in the communication activities.

Table 8 - INFRAMIX deliverables and target groups

Div	Deliverable name	Delivery date (M)	Related Results Id	Audience										
				Industry	Infr. Ops & Road auth	Public admin	Relevant Initiatives	EU&Nat org and Tech	Scientific & R+I com.	EC and EU stakeh	End users	Key influencers	General public	
D2.1	Requirements catalogue from the status quo analysis	6	R1	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			
D4.1	INFRAMIX plan for systems interaction, integration and testing	18	R2	X	X		X	X	X					
D3.1	Design and development of infrastructure elements	24	R3	X	X		X	X	X					
D3.3	HD maps and electronic road horizon (*)	24	R3	X	X		X	X	X	X				
D3.4	Implementation of traffic management strategies (*)	24	R3	X	X	X	X	X	X	X				
D3.5	New visual signs and elements	24	R3	X	X	X	X	X		X	X			
D5.4	Infrastructure classification scheme	26	R4	X	X	X	X	X	X	X				
D4.2	Demonstration phase and data delivery report (*)	30	R5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X				
D5.2	Users' appreciation results	36	R5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
D5.3	Evaluation results, impact analysis and new safety performance criteria for the road infrastructure	36	R5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
D6.4	Roadmap towards fully automated transport systems	36	R5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
D6.5	Exploitation plans (*)	36	R5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		

In addition, the project plans to publish 18 scientific papers in international journals or conferences. The below table shows a tentative list of schedule and contents related to these scientific papers:

Table 9 - INFRAMIX planned scientific publications

Paper Id	Issuing date	Related Results Id								
			Industry	Infr. Ops & Road auth	Public admin	Relevant Initiatives	EU&Nat org and Tech	Scientific & R+I com.	EC and EU stakeh	End users
P1	M12	R1	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
P2	M12	R1	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
P3	M12	R1	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
P4	M24	R2	X	X		X	X	X		
P5	M24	R2	X	X		X	X	X		
P6	M24	R3	X	X		X	X	X		
P7	M24	R3	X	X		X	X	X		
P8	M24	R3	X	X		X	X	X		
P9	M24	R3	X	X		X	X	X		
P10	M24	R3	X	X		X	X	X		
P11	M36	R4	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
P12	M36	R4	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
P13	M36	R5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
P14	M36	R5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
P15	M36	R5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
P16	M36	R5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
P17	M36	R5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
P18	M36	R4, R5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

6.4 Related initiatives

Several initiatives, both ongoing and future will be contacted to work on cross-fertilization, to align expectation and to avoid duplicities. Among them:

- interACT (www.interact-roadautomation.eu)
- BRAVE (www.brave-project.eu)
- TrustVehicle (www.trustvehicle.eu)

- L3Pilot (www.l3pilot.eu)
- CoEXist (www.h2020-coexist.eu)
- TransAID (www.transaid.eu)
- MAVEN (www.maven-its.eu)

During the first year, we expect to get in contact with at least 8 national or EU-scoped projects/initiatives. Please, check section 8.1 for extended KPI figures.

7. INFRAMIX events and visibility at external events

The INFRAMIX events will come as a dissemination support to project objectives. They will help in spreading the project outputs to the respective target audiences, facilitate valuable feedback from respective stakeholders, and provide ground for discussion and brainstorming.

7.1 INFRAMIX events

Three major events will be organised by INFRAMIX to underpin the communication and dissemination of the project. Specifically, two **Stakeholder Workshops** will be held in **M24 at the Spanish test site** and in **M29 at the Austrian test site** aiming to efficiently disseminate preliminary findings and collect targeted feedback from key-actors.

An **INFRAMIX Conference** will be organised in Austria towards the end of the project, where INFRAMIX final results will be presented to approximately 100 attendees through technical presentations while technologies will be showcased through live demonstrations and an exhibition. A press conference will also be held in the context of the INFRAMIX final event to spread the word about project results and solutions to non-technical audiences and the media. To secure wide after-event dissemination, the workshops and final conference materials, i.e. technical presentations and reports on performed discussions, will be available at the INFRAMIX website.

7.2 INFRAMIX End Users' Group events

For engaging as many stakeholders as possible, collecting their direct feedback and efficiently disseminate project results and evolutions, an End Users' Group will be early created in the framework of Task 6.3. The Group will be open to joining and will give to its participants the choice of simply receiving information or being more actively involved in INFRAMIX deployment. The latter will comprise the core members of the End Users' Group. These Core members will be requested to provide direct feedback on every opportunity (i.e. through participation at INFRAMIX Stakeholder Workshops), to assist the INFRAMIX consortium to efficiently evaluate the proposed technologies and perform the required corrections according to the end user needs and expectations. This group is also expected to help in reaching consensus regarding the proposed solutions for key issues such as infrastructure classification. The aforementioned engagement activities are highly expected to increase user acceptance and in complement with the INFRAMIX exploitation activities (Task 6.4) to ensure wide market penetration of the proposed solutions. A first list of the Core End Users' Group members, willing to closely cooperate with INFRAMIX consortium, will be available in M09 and included in D6.3.

7.3 External events

Besides the already planned INFRAMIX workshops and the final event, several special sessions and workshops dedicated to INFRAMIX will also be organised in the framework of well-known conferences and congresses, such as the ITS European and World Congresses even from the 1st year of INFRAMIX.

INFRAMIX will be disseminated primarily through presentations and posters at relevant transport sector conferences, workshops and special meetings of AUVSI, CEDR, the ASECAP days, etc. "Marketing-oriented" presentations will also be performed at industry events and trades. The project brochure and give-aways will be distributed on different occasions and posters will be displayed in exhibitions.

The following table lists relevant potential events for the coming years:

Table 10 – Potential events for INFRAMIX

Event	Date	Place
Mobile World Congress	Feb (annual)	Barcelona, Spain
Advanced Autonomous Drive Conference	Feb 2018	San Francisco, USA
Intertraffic	Mar 2018	Amsterdam, NL
CIHT Annual Conference	Mar 2018	London, UK
TRA Transport Research Arena ³	Apr 2018	Vienna, Austria
International Transport Forum (ITF)	May 2018	Leipzig, Germany
International VDI conference on Automated Driving	May 2018	Düsseldorf, Germany
ASECAP Days	Jun 2018	Ljubljana, Slovenia
The Future of Transportation conference	Jun 2018	Köln, Germany
IEEE Vehicular Technology Conference	Jun 2018	Porto, Portugal
Autonomous Vehicle Test & Development	Jun 2018	Stuttgart, Germany
AVS 2017, San Francisco ⁴	Jul 2018	San Francisco, USA
ITS World Congress ⁵	Sep 2018	Copenhagen, Denmark
IOT Solutions World Congress	Oct (annual)	Barcelona, Spain
Smart Mobility Congress	Nov 2018	Barcelona, Spain
IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Conference	Nov 2018	Mauai, Hawaii, USA
Highways UK	Nov 2018	Birmingham, UK
PIARC World Road Congress	Oct 2019	Paris, France
ITS European Congress ⁶	N/A	N/A
Transportation Research Board Annual Meeting	N/A	N/A
ECTRI	N/A	N/A
European Transport Forum	N/A	N/A

³ Confirmed participation
⁴ Already presented in 2017 edition
⁵ Already presented in 2017 edition
⁶ 2018 edition combined with ITSWC

8. Measuring the effectiveness of activities

8.1 Summary of Key performance indicators

The effectiveness of INFRAMIX strategic approach and planning for communication and dissemination will be constantly evaluated through dedicated performance indicators that are shown in Table 11 and will be thoroughly reported in the D6.1 and its periodic updates.

Table 11 - INFRAMIX Key Performance Indicators for Communication & Dissemination

Activity and criteria (KPI)		Expected performance		
		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Definition of Communication Strategy and Tools (Task 6.1)	Communication Strategy & plan: Annual project review	Positive	Positive (update)	Positive (update)
	Website – number of visitors (unique, returning)	250/mont h	400/mont h	400/mont h
	Twitter – total number of followers	100	150	200
	LinkedIn – total members of group members	80	120	180
	Social Media Campaigns –total number	1	1	
	No of project videos – total number	≥ 0	≥ 1	≥ 1 (Updated)
	Quantity of media coverage achieved ⁷	≥ 10	≥ 10	≥ 20
Dissemination and communication to community (Task 6.2)	No of peer reviewed publications	≥ 3	≥ 7	≥ 8
	Readership results	150	200	350
	No of End Users attending INFRAMIX workshops		≥ 40	≥ 40
	No of project events in conferences/congresses	≥ 1	≥ 2	≥ 2
	No of presentations	≥10	≥18	≥20
	No of demonstrations/exhibitions		≥1	≥2
	No of final event attendees			≥ 100
Networking/ User engagement activities (Task 6.3)	No of End User Group participants	≥ 20	≥ 60	≥ 100
	No of industry representatives involved	≥ 5	≥ 10	≥ 15
	No of associations & organisations involved	≥ 3	≥ 5	≥6
	No of projects contacted	≥ 8	≥ 8	≥ 10
	No of liaison activities performed	≥ 5	≥ 10	≥ 10
	No of discussions in fora, committees & organisations	≥ 5	≥ 5	≥ 5
	No of Standardisation bodies reached	≥2	≥2	≥2

⁷ Number of media appearances

⁸ Number of different individuals or entities

8.2 Activities performed during the first 6 months of project

Although the project is in an initial phase, several dissemination actions have already been planned/executed. A summary is included in the following table:

Table 12 - INFRAMIX dissemination actions up to month 6

Date	Type/ Description/ Title	Audience	Countries addressed	Size of Audience	Partner responsible / involved
Jul'17	Press release: project kick-off ⁹	General	Global	Massive	All
Jul'17	AVS 2017, San Francisco, Break-out session (infrastructure classification scheme)	Industry, Technical, Scientific	Global	Targeted	ICCS
Sep'17	Newspaper article: <i>Mundo innovadores (El Mundo) La autopista para el coche autónomo se prepara con sensores en la AP7</i> ¹⁰ see Annex	General	Spain	Massive	AAE
Sep'17	Media coverage of the project ¹¹ see Annex	General	Spain	Massive	AAE

⁹ In detail, some partners, as for example, AAE or ATE, have produced important media impact, with multiple media references:

(SPA)http://www.eldiario.es/economia/Autopistas-Abertis-Inframix-infraestructura-subsuencionado_0_669133542.html

(SPA)http://www.expansion.com/agencia/europa_press/2017/07/26/20170726134209.html

(SPA)<http://www.europapress.es/economia/noticia-autopistas-abertis-participa-proyecto-inframix-infraestructura-vial-subsuencionado-45-millones-20170726134211.html>

(SPA)<http://www.vilaweb.cat/noticies/autopistas-abertis-participa-en-el-proyecto-inframix-dinfraestructura-vial-subsuencionat-amb-45-milions/>

(SPA)http://www.teinteresa.es/dinero/Autopistas-Abertis-Inframix-infraestructura-subsuencionado_0_1839416406.html

(SPA)<http://www.eleconomista.es/economia/noticias/8520605/07/17/Autopistas-Abertis-participa-en-el-proyecto-Inframix-de-infraestructura-vial-subsuencionado-con-45-millones.html>

(SPA)<http://www.diarosigloxxi.com/texto-ep/mostrat/20170726134209/autopistas-abertis-participa-proyecto-inframix-infraestructura-vial-subsuencionado-45-millones>

(SPA)<http://www.aldia.cat/espanya/noticia-autopistas-abertis-participa-proyecto-inframix-dinfraestructura-vial-subsuencionat-amb-45-milions-20170726135923.html>

(SPA)<https://www.invertia.com/es/-/economia-autopistas-abertis-participa-en-el-proyecto-inframix-de-infraestructura-vial-subsuencionado-con-4-5-millones>

(SPA)http://www.lainformacion.com/economia-negocios-y-finanzas/transporte/transporte-por-carretera/Autopistas-Abertis-Inframix-infraestructura-subsuencionado_0_1048095866.html

(SPA)<http://www.bolsamania.com/noticias/empresas/economia-autopistas-abertis-participa-en-el-proyecto-inframix-de-infraestructura-vial-subsuencionado-con-45-millones--2787888.html>

(GER)<http://www.car-it.com/forschungsteam-simuliert-mischverkehr/id-0051898>

¹⁰ (SPA)<http://www.elmundo.es/cataluna/2017/09/12/59b7af39e5fdea22528b45ea.html>

¹¹ Depending on the media, for general public or industry focused

(SPA)<http://www.levante-emv.com/economia/2017/10/09/proyecto-inframix-prepara-camino-vehiculos/1625788.html>

(SPA)<http://www.laopinioncoruna.es/economia/2017/10/09/proyecto-inframix-prepara-camino-vehiculos/1224568.html>

(SPA)<http://www.farodevigo.es/economia/2017/10/09/proyecto-inframix-prepara-camino-vehiculos/1764244.html>

(SPA)<http://www.diarioinformacion.com/economia/2017/10/09/proyecto-inframix-prepara-camino-vehiculos/1944557.html>

Oct'17	ITS WC SIS with CoExist and TransAID. See Annex VI	Industry, Technical, Scientific	Global	Targeted	ICCS
Planned actions					
Nov/Dec'17	Newspaper article: (SPA) <i>Diari de Tarragona</i> , interview to Carlos Pitarque, Technology and innovation Director at Autopistas	General	Spain	Massive	AAE
Apr'18	TRA invited session with CoExist and TransAID	Industry, Technical, Scientific, EC&EU stakeholders	European	N/A	ICCS, ATE
Apr'18	TRA paper for INFRAMIX	Industry, Technical, Scientific, EC&EU stakeholders	European	N/A	ICCS, ATE

(SPA)<http://www.diariodeibiza.es/economia/2017/10/09/proyecto-inframix-prepara-camino-vehiculos/944965.html>

(SPA)<http://www.diariodemallorca.es/economia/2017/10/09/proyecto-inframix-prepara-camino-vehiculos/1254175.html>

(SPA)<http://www.diariodemallorca.es/economia/2017/10/09/proyecto-inframix-prepara-camino-vehiculos/1254175.html>

(SPA)<http://www.laopiniondezamora.es/economia/2017/10/09/proyecto-inframix-prepara-camino-vehiculos/1036809.html>

(SPA)<http://www.laopinion.es/economia/2017/10/09/proyecto-inframix-prepara-camino-vehiculos/815509.html>

(SPA)<http://www.laopiniondemurcia.es/economia/2017/10/09/proyecto-inframix-prepara-camino-vehiculos/865980.html>

9. Conclusion

Communication and Dissemination activities are of major importance for the INFRAMIX project and therefore a significant number of communication and dissemination activities are planned for its duration. To coordinate the activities there is a need for a concise strategy. In this deliverable, the strategy and plan designed especially for the INFRAMIX project is presented. The goals of the dissemination activity have been set, the dissemination materials to be used have been designed and the dissemination channels to reach the specified target groups have been also defined. All these dissemination elements are included in a concise roadmap that is supervised by the Dissemination Leader according to specific procedures. A major focus is put on the project website which is designed to be as user friendly and attractive as possible. Finally, the deliverable presents the basic procedures for the organisation, control and execution of all project dissemination activities.

10. References

- [1] "Wikipedia, Wikipedia," [Online]. Available: <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia>.
- [2] INFRAMIX, "INFRAMIX Project Consortium Agreement," 2017.
- [3] INFRAMIX, "D1.1 Quality Management Plan," 2017.
- [4] INFRAMIX, "INFRAMIX Project Description of Work," 2017.

ANNEX I – H2020 guidelines

H2020 Dissemination Guidelines

For Horizon 2020 projects the reference document for communication, dissemination and exploitation activities is the Grant Agreement (GA), and namely Articles 29 (Dissemination of results — Open access — Visibility of EU funding) and 38 (Promoting the action — Visibility of EU funding).

Promoting the action — Visibility of EU funding: Communication activities by beneficiaries

Regarding article 38, these are the rules to follow:

Obligation to promote the action and its results

The beneficiaries must promote the action and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in a strategic and effective manner.

Before engaging in a communication activity expected to have a major media impact, the beneficiaries must inform INEA.

Information on EU funding — Obligation and right to use the EU emblem

Unless INEA requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any communication activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must:

(a) Display the EU emblem and

(b) Include the following text:

For communication activities: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 723265”.

For infrastructure, equipment and major results: “This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 723265”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from INEA.

This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use.

Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this agreement, the grant may be reduced.

Dissemination of results — Open access — Visibility of EU funding

Regarding article 29, these are the rules to follow:

Obligation to disseminate results

Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must — as soon as

possible — ‘disseminate’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium).

A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give advance notice to the other beneficiaries of — unless agreed otherwise — at least 45 days, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.

Any other beneficiary may object within — unless agreed otherwise — 30 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests.

If a beneficiary intends not to protect its results, it may [...] need to formally notify the *Innovation and Networks Executive Agency (INEA)* before dissemination takes place.

Open access to scientific publications

Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- The terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- The name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- The publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- A persistent identifier.

Information on EU funding — Obligation and right to use the EU emblem

Unless INEA requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

(a) Display the EU emblem and

(b) Include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 723265”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

For the purposes of their obligations under this agreement, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from INEA.

This does not however give them the right to exclusive use.

Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

Disclaimer excluding INEA responsibility

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author’s view and that INEA is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this agreement, the grant may be reduced.

Open access to scientific publications

Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- The terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- The name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- The publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- A persistent identifier.

Communication versus Dissemination

Excerpt from <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/support/faqs/faq-933.html>

Dissemination is the public disclosure of the results of the project in any medium. Disclosure may sound passive, like a shop opening up, but it is an activity, like a shopkeeper attracting customers. It is a process of promotion and awareness-raising right from the beginning of a project. It makes research results known to various stakeholder groups (like research peers, industry and other commercial actors, professional organisations, policymakers) in a targeted way, to enable them to use the results in their own work. This process must be planned and organised at the beginning of each project, usually in a dissemination plan.

Communication means taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. The aim is to reach out to society as a whole and in particular to some specific audiences while demonstrating how EU funding contributes to tackling societal challenges.

ANNEX II - Other Social media

Facebook

Description

Facebook is a social networking service launched in February 2004, owned and operated by Facebook, Inc. Facebook has more than 2 billion monthly active users as of June 2017. As of April 2016, Facebook was the most popular social networking site in the world, based on the number of active user accounts. Users must register before using the site, after which they may create a personal profile, add other users as friends, and exchange messages, including automatic notifications when they update their profile. Additionally, users may join common-interest user groups, organized by workplace, school or college, or other characteristics.

Users can create profiles with photos, lists of personal interests, contact information, and other personal information. Users can communicate with friends and other users through private or public messages and a chat feature. They can also create and join interest groups and "like pages", some of which are maintained by organizations as a means of advertising. A 2012 Pew Internet and American Life study identified that between 20–30% of Facebook users are "power users" who frequently link, poke, post and tag themselves and others.

The like button is a social networking feature, allowing users to express their appreciation of content such as status updates, comments, photos, and advertisements.

Use

Given its popularity as social network, this tool could have an important role in the communication and dissemination activities. However, currently, the general profile of the user as well as its lack of focus on professional activities does **not recommend** this network for scientific or technical dissemination.

Wikipedia

Description

Wikipedia is a collaboratively edited, multilingual, free Internet encyclopaedia supported by the non-profit Wikimedia Foundation. Its 24 million articles, over 4.1 million in the English Wikipedia, are written collaboratively by volunteers around the world. Almost all of its articles can be edited by anyone with access to the site. [...] It has become the largest and most popular general reference work on the Internet, ranking sixth globally among all websites on Alexa and having an estimated 365 million readers worldwide. [1]

Use

Although it is not a social network, Wikipedia is seen by many as a key entrance point for the understanding of scientific and technical concepts. In this way, it could be interesting to include a page to explain the project, the goals, achievements and updates, with emphasis in the following factors:

- Technical concepts related to the issues of the project: inductive charging, electric vehicles, batteries, etc
- Other internet tools related to the project (Twitter, LinkedIn, Web site, etc.)

Given the nature and rules of Wikipedia, especially concerning the revision and approval procedures, it is important to avoid that the entry in Wikipedia may have seen as just a promotion page, so both contents and language use should be carefully used. In addition,

Wikipedia is a tertiary information source, which is fed by secondary information sources (independent from the primary information source, which are the originators of the information). This means that before establishing a Wikipedia entry, several secondary information sources should inform about INFRAMIX.

SlideShare

Description

SlideShare is a Web 2.0 based slide hosting service. Users can upload files privately or publicly in the following file formats: PowerPoint, PDF, Keynote or OpenDocument presentations. Slide decks can then be viewed on the site itself, on hand held devices or embedded on other sites. Launched on October 4, 2006, the website is considered to be similar to YouTube, but for slideshows. The website was originally meant to be used for businesses to share slides among employees more easily, but it has since expanded to also become a host of a large number of slides that are uploaded merely to entertain. Although the website is primarily a slide hosting service, it also supports documents, PDFs, videos and webinars. SlideShare also provides users the ability to rate, comment on, and share the uploaded content...

SlideShare was voted among the World's Top 10 tools for education & e-learning in 2010.

On May 2012, SlideShare announced that it was to be acquired by LinkedIn.

Use

Although it was originally not a social network, SlideShare is seen by many as a key entrance point for the understanding of scientific and technical concepts. In this way, it could be interesting to include a page to explain the project, the goals, achievements and updates, with emphasis in the following factors:

In this case, it is foreseen that presentations material related to the project findings should be made available. Using the SlideShare functionalities, a channel with its followers could become a platform for disseminating the project by sharing the public presentations to a wider audience, as well as an additional starting point for the audience, by using the right terms for the search.

Open access repository

Description

According Wikipedia an open access repository is a digital platform that holds research output and provide free, immediate and permanent access to research results to anyone to use, download and distribute. To facilitate open access such repositories must be interoperable according to the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH). Search engines harvest the content of open access repositories, constructing a database of worldwide, free of charge available research.

Use

As opposed to simple institutional repository or disciplinary repository open access repositories provides free access to research to users outside the institutional community are one of the recommended ways to achieve the open access vision described in the Budapest Open Access Initiative definition of open access. This is sometimes referred to as "green" route to open access.

Following the H2020 rules regarding the publication of Dissemination information, including documents, articles and datasets (if any is available), INFRAMIX will publish its information in a permanent Open Access repository. At the current moment the initial candidates

include: ZENODO (a joint initiative of OpenAIRE and the CERN), Digital Commons, OALibrary (Open Access Library) or Open-Science-Repository. Among other considerations, being ready to be indexed by Google Scholar will be an important factor in the election.